

OPTIMIZATION OF THE TORSIONAL-RIGIDITY
AND -STRENGTH FOR FIBER-
REINFORCED COMPOSITE CYLINDERS

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The design optimization problems for the torsional rigidity and torsional strength of fiber-reinforced composite cylinders such as filament-wound cylinders are considered. As for the elastic buckling torque of composite cylinders which can be treated as orthotropic cylinders, the author's analytical study published previously is partly introduced, and then the structural indices, which are usable for design optimization of the rigidity and strength, are derived from his results (1) - (3).

For helically wound cylinders, the filament-winding angle is taken as a typical design parameter, if the basic material properties of a filament sheet as the constitutional unit of cylinders are given a priori. A procedure for finding its optimum winding angle is also developed.

As numerical examples, glass-filament and carbon-filament wound cylinders are taken. Those optimum winding angles are calculated for the fiber volume fractions ranging from 30 to 70%. For the cylinders with smaller radius to thickness ratios, the optimum winding angle will be $\pm 45^\circ$ for conventional glass fiber, carbon fiber and matrix materials; on the other hand, for the case of relatively short cylinders with larger ratios of radius to thickness, the optimum winding angle for torsional rigidity and buckling strength will be ca $\pm 69^\circ$ or $\pm 61^\circ$ for glass fiber and $\pm 71^\circ$ or $\pm 67^\circ$ for carbon fiber, respectively, for a wide variation of fiber volume fractions mentioned above. It is to be noted that these optimum winding angles will not largely depend on the fiber volume fraction.

1. Introduction

Fiber-reinforced composite materials (FRCM) are now being widely used in various engineering structures because of their high specific modulus and strength. Generally speaking, any structure consists of three basic and simple structural elements: bar, plate and cylinder (shell). Cylinder is a typical three-dimensional element whilst bar and plate are one- and two-dimensional one, respectively. The optimization study for these structural elements made of FRCM is of significant importance. The optimization studies on bars and plates have been published by several authors, but it seems that the systematic studies for FRCM cylinders have not yet been done satisfactorily.

Composite cylinders are usually fabricated by moulding technique such as symmetrical filament-winding (FW), tape winding or cloth-lamination. Therefore, the elasticity and strength of fiber reinforced composite cylinder-walls exhibit generally an axi-symmetric orthotropy, whose principal directions of orthotropy are the axial, circumferential and radial directions.

In a design course of such cylinders, an appropriate design objective function (DOF) or structural index (SI), which may involve a number of design variables, should be usually selected at an early stage. It may be structural weight, life, cost or so. The fact that it often contains many design variables is a merit in composite materials design. The optimization procedure is to optimize DOF or SI under some given constraint conditions. The amount of work and difficulty for optimization procedure will largely depend upon the validity of DOF or SI selected.

The author has been studying the structural indices for the loading cases of compression, bending, side pressure and torsion, and published an optimization study of cylinder for compression (4). For orthotropic cylinders under torsion, however, the structural indices which are quite suitable for optimization procedure, have not yet been studied.

Orthotropic cylinders have two fracture modes: shear fracture of skin materials and buckling failure. For optimization problems in which the buckling failure predominates, the corresponding SI will be found by making use of the formulas for buckling strength which were previously derived in closed forms by the present author (1). Hence, the author's analytical method of finding the torsional buckling strength of a thin-walled orthotropic cylinder is briefly outlined and the author's formulas are introduced.

In the succeeding chapters, the SI-formulas for cylinders, which can be designed by torsional buckling load only and have homogeneous elastic properties, are derived; and then the

optimizing index for cylinders which should be designed for both requirements of torsional-rigidity and -strength is also studied. For symmetric helically filament-wound cylinders, the procedure of finding the optimum winding angle is developed and followed by some numerical examples for glass- and carbon-filament-wound cylinders.

2. Torsional Buckling Load of Orthotropic Cylinders

Since the buckling of a thin-walled cylinder will produce a finite deflection of skin, it would be better to apply the so-called finite deflection theory for the analysis. But because of high non-linearity of the problem it seems to be impossible to obtain a closed form solution for buckling load. On the other hand, the author had already succeeded to derive the explicit formulas of torsional buckling load, based on the small deflection theory (1). It is also known that small deflection theory can be applied approximately in practice, especially for torsion problems of orthotropic cylinders. Moreover for the present purpose of design optimization of cylinders, it is most desirable to use explicit formulas for buckling strength. Thus, the author's formulas are used in this study.

Theoretical Results

A fiber-reinforced composite orthotropic cylinder subjected to torsion at both ends is considered. Let the skin (cylinder wall) have an axi-symmetric orthotropy, and also have a middle surface as a neutral plane for bending. On this middle surface of skin, two axes, x and y , are taken parallel to axial and circumferential directions, respectively. Two principal directions of orthotropy of skin, 1 and 2 are also parallel to these axes (Fig. 1). Let both ends of a cylinder be subjected to uniformly distributed circumferential shear force per unit width, S , at buckling. Twisting moment at buckling, T , is given by

$$T = S\pi d^2/2 \quad (1)$$

Experimental evidences show that the angle of inclination of the buckling wave peak with respect to the cylinder axis, ϕ , is small as around $5^\circ - 20^\circ$ (Fig. 3). Hence, assuming $\tan^2 \phi < \alpha_2/\alpha_1$, the author has obtained the following results (1) - (3) (Refer to Appendix).

a. In short cylinder region:

$$\text{For both ends supported and if } J < 5.5; \quad B = 1.18J^{1/4}, \quad n = 2.31J^{-1/4} \quad (2)$$

For both ends fixed and if $J < 7.8$:

$$B = 1.29J^{1/4}, \quad n = 2.62J^{-1/4} \quad (3)$$

b. In long cylinder region:

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{For both ends supported and if } J > 5.5 \\ \text{For both ends fixed and if } J > 7.8 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l}) \\) \\) \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} B = 0.77J^{1/2} \\ n = 2 \end{array} \quad (4)$$

From these formulas, the distributed shear force and torque at buckling are easily calculated.

If the skin material has the homogeneous elastic properties over the thickness, we have

$$B = (Sl/E_1t^2)(E_1/E_2)^{1/2} \quad J = (tl^2/d^3)(E_2/E_1)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where v_1v_2 is assumed to be negligible small compared with unity. We obtain

a. In short cylinder region:

for both ends supported and if $J < 5.5$:

$$\begin{array}{l} \tau = S/t = 1.18(E_1t/l)(t/d)^{1/4}(l/d)^{1/2}(E_2/E_1)^{5/8} \\ n = 2.31(tl^2/d^3)^{-1/4}(E_2/E_1)^{-1/8} \end{array} \quad (6)$$

b. In long cylinder region:

for both ends supported and if $J > 5.5$:

$$\begin{array}{l} \tau = S/t = 0.77(E_1E_2^3)^{1/4}(t/d)^{3/2} \\ n = 2 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l}) \\) \\) \end{array} \quad (7)$$

For both ends fixed, we obtain similar formulas whose numerical coefficients only are different from those in above formulas.

For a very slender tube, Greenhill found a global buckling pattern as shown in Fig. 4 which has no local deformation of section and accompanies a bending deflection with twist (5). He gave the following buckling torque formula:

$$T = 2\pi E_1 I / l \quad (8)$$

where E_1 is the flexural rigidity of tube and I is given by

$$I = \pi r^3 t [1 + (t/2r)^2] \quad (9)$$

This buckling pattern does not happen in most cases except very long tube.

3. Structural Index for Homogeneous Orthotropic Cylinders which are Designed by Torsional Buckling Strength only

In many filament-wound cylinders and multicloth-laminated cylinders, the elastic properties of their skins are considered to be approximately homogeneous over their thickness. We consider here a cylinder whose skin has the homogeneous elastic properties and whose design requirement is the torsional moment T^* .

Let the cylinder be simply supported at both ends. The total mass of cylinder, M , is given by $M = \rho \pi d t l$ where ρ is the skin density. Since for three dimensional variables, d , t and l , we have only one condition $T \geq T^*$, we have to specify two of them a priori. Thus, when the external torque, T^* , and any two of d , t and l are specified a priori, the structural index, SI , so as to minimize the mass M is found as follows:

For short cylinders with $J < 5.5$:

a. if T^* , l and d are specified: $SI = (E_1^3 E_2^5)^{1/18} / \rho \quad (10)$

b. if T^* , l and t are specified: $SI = (E_1^3 E_2^5)^{1/10} / \rho \quad (11)$

For long cylinders with $J > 5.5$:

a. if T^* , l and d are specified: $SI = (E_1 E_2^3)^{1/10} / \rho \quad (12)$

b. if T^* , l and t are specified: $SI = (E_1 E_2^3)^{1/2} / \rho \quad (13)$

The cylinder which has larger SI becomes lighter.

For the case of cylinders fixed at their both ends, we obtain the same SI as above, except the region of J .

4. Optimizing Index for Cylinders which should be Designed for Both Requirements of Torsional-Rigidity and -Strength

We consider a design optimization problem of a symmetrical filament-wound cylinder such that it will have a minimum weight on condition of the required torsional rigidity, R^* , and torsional moment, T^* . Let the cylinder be simply supported at both ends.

There are two fracture modes: shear fracture of skin material and elastic buckling failure. The following two cases, a and b, are possible.

a. The case where the Skin Shear Fracture precedes the Buckling Failure

In this case we have

$$R^* = 2\pi G t r^3, \quad T^* = 2\pi \tau t r^2 \quad (14)$$

Eliminating t and r in the cylinder mass $M = \pi \rho d t l$ with above conditions, we obtain

$$M = \rho G l T^* / (R^* \tau^2) \quad (15)$$

If G and τ are given as functions of winding angle, θ , the minimum weight design is conducted by maximizing the following SI;

$$SI = \tau^2 / \rho G \quad (16)$$

b. The Case where the Skin Buckling precedes the Skin Shear Fracture

In this case we have two regions of finding structural indices.

1. For short cylinder region with $J < 5.5$:

$$T = 1.853 E_1 t^2 l (E_2 / E_1)^{5/8} (t/d)^{1/4} (d/l)^{3/2} = T^*, \quad (17)$$

$$R^* = 2\pi G t r^3, \quad M = 2\pi \rho t r l$$

Eliminating t and r from above equations, we can obtain the optimizing structural index:

$$SI = (E_1^3 E_2^5 G^4)^{1/22} / \rho, \quad M \propto 1/(SI), \quad (18)$$

2. For long cylinder region with $J > 5.5$:

We find similarly

$$SI = (E_1 E_2^3 G^4)^{1/14} / \rho, \quad M \propto 1/(SI). \quad (19)$$

5. Optimum Winding-Angle for Symmetrical Helically Filament-Wound Cylinders

For helically filament-wound cylinders, their skins can be considered such that they are constructed by parallel laminating of some number of bias-laminate unit as shown in Fig. 5, in which a bias unit is composed of two unidirectional filament sheets with ply-angle 2θ . If this assumption will hold, the elastic properties of the cylinder skin will be the same as those of the bias-laminate unit. We next consider the case where such treatment is allowed.

Fig. 6 (a) shows a basic unidirectional filament sheet of thickness $t_0/2$. When its stress-strain law with respect to its principal directions, L and T , is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_L &= \sigma_L/E_L - \nu_T \sigma_T/E_T, & \epsilon_T &= \sigma_T/E_T - \nu_L \sigma_L/E_L, \\ & & &) \\ & & &) \\ \gamma_{LT} &= \tau_{LT}/G_{LT} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

that of a bias-laminate unit and then of cylinder-skin referred to the principal directions, 1 and 2, is derived as follows:

$$\epsilon_1 = \sigma_1/E_1 - \nu_2 \sigma_2/E_2, \quad \epsilon_2 = \sigma_2/E_2 - \nu_1 \sigma_1/E_1, \quad \gamma_{12} = \tau_{12}/G, \quad (21)$$

where

$$E_1 = C_{11} - C_{12}^2/C_{22}, \quad E_2 = C_{22} - C_{12}^2/C_{11}, \quad G = C_{33}, \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{11} &= 3K_1 + K_2 + K_3 \cos 2\theta + K_4 \cos 4\theta, \\
C_{22} &= 3K_1 + K_2 - K_3 \cos 2\theta + K_4 \cos 4\theta, \\
C_{12} &= K_1 - K_2 - K_4 \cos 4\theta, \\
C_{33} &= K_1 + K_2 - K_4 \cos 4\theta,
\end{aligned}
\tag{23}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
K_1 &= (E_L + E_T + 2E_L \nu_T) / (8\lambda) \\
K_2 &= (\lambda G_{LT} - E_L \nu_T) / (2\lambda) \\
K_3 &= (E_L - E_T) / (2\lambda) \\
K_4 &= (E_L + E_T - 2E_L \nu_T - 4\lambda G_{LT}) / (8\lambda) \\
\lambda &= 1 - \nu_L \nu_T. \quad \nu_L E_T = \nu_T E_L.
\end{aligned}
\tag{24}$$

θ is the winding-angle referred to the cylinder axis (Fig. 5 and 6). These elastic constants, E_1 , E_2 and G , are used for optimization of structural indices SI which were already derived in the preceding paragraphs.

6. Numerical Examples

As numerical examples, glass filament-wound cylinders and carbon filament-wound cylinders are considered. The optimum winding-angle for both requirements of torsional rigidity and strength is calculated.

Elastic properties of unidirectional glass- and carbon-filament reinforced epoxy composites, which are the basic data for this analysis, are given in Table I and II. The latter was cited from the data by Dean and Turner (6).

Two modes of skin material fracture and buckling failure are discussed separately.

a. Optimum Winding-Angle of a Filament-Wound Cylinder for Torsional Rigidity and Shear Fracture Strength

According to several torsion test results on glass filament-wound cylinders whose fiber volume fraction ranges from 50 to 60%, thickness is 3 to 4 mm and diameter about 100 - 150 mm (7), the torsional shear strength can be empirically expressed by

$$\tau(\theta) = \tau_0(1 + k\sin 2\theta), \quad (25)$$

where

$$\tau_0 = 5 \text{ kg/mm}^2 \quad \text{and } k = 5.$$

On the other hand, the skin shear modulus, $G(\theta)$, is given by

$$G(\theta) = K_1 + K_2 - K_4 \cos 4\theta. \quad (26)$$

Thus, from paragraph 4.a, the stationary condition of $SI = \tau^2/\rho G$ with respect to θ gives

$$\cos 2\theta = 0, \quad (27)$$

or
$$\sin 2\theta = k(K_1 + K_2 - K_4)/(2K_4). \quad (28)$$

The second condition has no real root of θ for the present composites tabulated. The first condition gives a root $\theta = \pi/4$, independent of the skin material properties. This solution of $\pm 45^\circ$ winding angle is very simple and instinctive. It seems essentially to come from the netting mechanism.

b. Optimum Angle of Glass Filament-Wound and Carbon Filament-Wound Cylinders designed for Torsional Rigidity and Buckling Strength

The optimizing structural index in this case is given by the Equations (18) and (19). When the elastic properties (E_L, E_T, ν_L, G_{LT}) of the basic unidirectional filament sheet as shown in Table I and II are provided, the structural index becomes a function of winding angle θ only. Using Eqs. (18), (19), (22), (23) and (24), we can perform the optimization analysis.

We assume the thickness of every interlayer between filament sheets in a cylinder skin to be negligible small. Then the fiber volume fraction (V_f) and density of skins of these cylinders are considered to be the same as those of the basic filament sheets given in Table I and II. The density of a cylinder wall, which is given by

$$\rho = \rho_f V_f + \rho_m V_m = (\rho_f - \rho_m) V_f + \rho_m, \quad (29)$$

does not depend on the winding angle.

Table III and IV show the results calculated on the glass filament-wound cylinders (GFWC) and carbon filament-wound cylinders (CFWC), respectively, which were made of the basic filament sheets given in Table I and II.

For three fiber volume fractions $V_f = 0.3, 0.5$ and 0.7 , the optimum winding angles, θ_o , and the corresponding optimum structural indices, SI_o , were found in both regions of $J < 5.5$ and $J > 5.5$. J is a parameter concerned with Young's moduli of skin, E_1 and E_2 , and cylinder dimensions of diameter d , skin thickness t and length l . From the condition:

$$J = (E_2/E_1)^{1/2} (tl^2/d^3) \gtrless 5.5$$

we have

$$tl^2/d^3 \gtrless 5.5 (E_1/E_2)^{1/2} \quad (30)$$

where as the modulus ratio E_1/E_2 , the value corresponding to the optimum winding angle should be taken. The condition for J value in Table III and IV are rewritten as Eq. (30).

As expected, Table III and IV show that the optimum value of SI increases with the fiber volume fraction. It is very interesting to see that the optimum winding angle does not nearly vary with the fiber volume fraction V_f in a range of 30 to 70% in GFW-cylinders and CFW-cylinders.

Comparison between these two kinds of cylinders tells us that in spite of large difference in Young's modulus between these cylinders GFWC and CFWC, there are not significant differences in the optimum winding-angle, but on the other hand the optimum structural indices of CFWC are almost twice larger than those of GFWC, i.e. CFWC have a great merit for weight saving.

7. Conclusions

The optimization problems of orthotropic fiber-reinforced composite cylinders on condition of torsional rigidity and strength were considered.

Structural indices (SI), which are useful in practice for the design optimization of cylinders subjected to torsion, were derived from the present author's formulas for buckling strength.

In numerical examples for glass filament-wound cylinders (GFWC) and carbon filament-wound cylinders (CFWC), several interesting features have been found (Table III and IV).

For the case of optimization for torsional rigidity and skin shear fracture strength, the optimum winding-angle for these cylinders is $\pi/4$.

For the case of optimization for torsional rigidity and buckling strength:

- a. the optimum winding angles are ca. 69° ($J < 5.5$) and ca. 61° ($J > 5.5$) for GFWC ; ca. 71° ($J < 5.5$) and ca. 67° ($J > 5.5$) for CFWC.
- b. these angles do not nearly vary with the fiber volume fraction from 30 to 70%.
- c. the difference of winding-angle between GFWC and CFWC is not so great.
- d. the optimum values of SI for CFWC are nearly twice larger than those of GFWC. CFWC have a great merit for weight saving through the optimum design.
- e. the structural indices derived here are very useful for optimization procedure of cylinders under torsion.

The above formulas of SI could be easily extended to more general orthotropic composites cylinders, by introducing an equivalent homogeneous plate concept.

Nomenclature

- l, r and d = length, radius and diameter of cylinder,
- x, y = coordinate axes parallel to axial and circumferential directions, respectively,
- 1, 2 = suffices denoting two principal axes of orthotropy, parallel to x and y, respectively,
- α_1, α_2 = extensional rigidities of unit width skin for 1 and 2 directions, respectively,
- ν_1, ν_2 = Poisson's ratios for in-plane deformation of skin,
- β = shear rigidity of unit width skin for in-plane shear in 1 and 2 directions,
- D_1, D_2 = flexural rigidities of unit width skin in 1 and 2,

- μ_1, μ_2 = Poisson's ratios for bending deformation of skin,
 K = torsional rigidity of unit width skin,
 $\nu_1\alpha_2 = \nu_2\alpha_1, \mu_1D_2 = \mu_2D_1$: Maxwell relationships,
 $\lambda = 1 - \nu_1\nu_2$
 S = buckling shear force per unit width, distributed along the periphery,
 T = torsional moment at buckling,
 $B = (SI/\alpha_1\lambda)(\alpha_1\lambda/12D_2)^{1/2}$
 $J = (1/d)^2 [12D_2/(\alpha_1\lambda d^2)]^{1/2}$ } extended Donnell's notations,
 R^*, T^* = required torsional rigidity and moment,
 u, v, w = displacement components of a point $P(x, y, 0)$ on a middle surface, caused by buckling,
 $N_1, N_2, N_{12}, N_{21}, Q_1, Q_2$ = stress-resultants (internal force components) per unit width for x, y sections, where $N_{12} = N_{21}$,
 M_1, M_2, M_{12}, M_{21} = stress-couples (moment components per unit width) for x, y sections, where $M_{12} = M_{21}$,
 $e_1, e_2 ; g$ = strain components
 $\kappa_1, \kappa_2 ; \omega$ = curvatures and twist,
 n = number of circumferential waves,
 ϕ = inclination angle of buckling wave peak with respect to x -axis,
 λ_m = parameter,
 SI = structural index,
 SI_o = optimum structural index,
 θ = winding-angle,
 θ_o = optimum winding-angle.

For the case of homogeneous skin materials:

t = uniform thickness of skin

$E_1, E_2; G$ = Young's moduli and shear modulus of skin

$$\nu_1 = \mu_1, \quad \nu_2 = \mu_2, \quad \nu_1 E_2 = \nu_2 E_1,$$

$$\alpha_1 = E_1 t / \lambda, \quad \alpha_2 = E_2 t / \lambda, \quad \beta = Gt, \quad D_1 = E_1 t^3 / 12\lambda,$$

$$D_2 = E_2 t^3 / 12\lambda,$$

$$B = (Sl/E_1 t^2) (E_1/E_2)^{1/2}, \quad J = (t l^2/d^3) (E_2/E_1)^{1/2}$$

$\tau = S/t$ = shear strength of skin

M = total mass of a cylinder

ρ = density of skin or density of filament sheet

ρ_f, ρ_m = density of filament and matrix of a basic filament sheet, respectively,

V_f, V_m = volume fractions of filament and matrix of a filament sheet, respectively,

$E_L, E_T, \nu_L, \nu_T, G_{LT}$ = elastic constants of a basic filament sheet

$(\sigma_L, \sigma_T, \tau_{LT}), (\epsilon_L, \epsilon_T, \gamma_{LT})$ = stress and strain components for a basic filament sheet, respectively,

$(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \tau_{12}), (\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \gamma_{12})$ = stress and strain components for a bias-laminate unit, respectively,

$C_{11}, C_{22}, C_{12}, C_{33}$ = elastic compliances for skin,

K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4 = basic quantities encountered in compliances.

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Appendix

Method of Analysis

Let the composite material of a cylinder skin have an axisymmetric orthotropy and a middle surface. Let the cylinder be in an equilibrium state under some uniformly distributed shear force per unit width of circumference at both ends. When the applied torque (or the distributed circumferential shear force) reaches a characteristic value T (or S), a buckling occurs and the cylinder enters into a second neighboring equilibrium state under the same external load, accompanying a very small additional displacement (u, v, w) . This displacement will induce internal forces $(N_1, N_2, N_{12}, Q_1, Q_2)$ and internal moments (M_1, M_2, M_{12}) in a skin element as shown in Fig. 2. Our object is to find the critical load (buckling load) which enables such neighboring deformed equilibrium state to be possible.

The internal forces and moments on an element are expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} N_1 &= \alpha_1(e_1 + \nu_2 e_2), & N_2 &= \alpha_2(e_2 + \nu_1 e_1), & N_{12} &= N_{21} = \beta g, \\ M_1 &= D_1(\kappa_1 + \mu_2 \kappa_2), & M_2 &= D_2(\kappa_2 + \mu_1 \kappa_1), & M_{12} &= M_{21} = \omega \kappa / 2 \end{aligned} \quad (a)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} e_1 &= \partial u / \partial x, & e_2 &= \partial v / \partial y + w / r, & g &= \partial u / \partial y + \partial v / \partial x \\ \kappa_1 &= \partial^2 w / \partial x^2, & \kappa_2 &= \partial^2 w / \partial y^2, & \omega &= \partial^2 w / \partial x \partial y. \end{aligned} \quad (b)$$

The equilibrium conditions of a small element of the cylinder are given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial N_1 / \partial x + \partial N_{12} / \partial y &= 0, & \partial N_{12} / \partial x + \partial N_2 / \partial y &= 0, \\ \partial Q_1 / \partial x + \partial Q_2 / \partial y + (N_2 / r) - 2S \partial^2 w / \partial x \partial y &= 0, \\ \partial M_1 / \partial x + \partial M_{12} / \partial y - Q_1 &= 0, & \partial M_{12} / \partial x + \partial M_2 / \partial y - Q_2 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (c)$$

Rewriting Eq. (c) in terms of displacement components and eliminating u and v , we have an equation in terms of w .

$$\begin{aligned} D_1 \partial^4 F / \partial x^4 + (2D_1 \mu_2 + K) \partial^4 F / \partial x^2 \partial y^2 + D_2 \partial^4 F / \partial y^4 \\ + (\alpha_2 \lambda / r^2) \partial^4 w / \partial x^4 - 2S \partial^2 F / \partial x \partial y = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (d)$$

where

$$F = \partial^4 w / \partial x^4 + (\alpha_2 / \beta) (\lambda - 2\nu_1 \beta / \alpha_1) \partial^4 w / \partial x^2 \partial y^2 + (\alpha_2 / \alpha_1) \partial^4 w / \partial y^4 \quad (e)$$

The problem is now reduced in finding w which satisfies Eq. (d) subject to the boundary conditions for radial displacement w , and in deciding the buckling waveform which gives a minimum values of S .

A buckling waveform which has n wave length in the circumferential direction and shows a torsional wave form along the axis (Fig. 3), can be represented as:

$$u = \sum_m U_m \sin 2\phi, \quad v = \sum_m V_m \cos 2\phi, \quad w = \sum_m W_m \sin 2\phi$$

where

$$\phi = (ny/d) - (\lambda_m x/l)$$

(f)

Substituting Eq. (f) into Eq. (d), we obtain a characteristic equation of the eighth order of λ_m . The eigenvalue λ_m is determined for the boundary value problem of a simply supported or fixed end cylinder.

If the angle of inclination of the buckling wave peak is ϕ with respect to the cylinder axis, $\tan \phi = \lambda_m d / (nl)$. Generally, ϕ is less than 45° and is around $5^\circ - 20^\circ$ from experimental evidences. So $\tan^2 \phi$ will be always smaller than unity. With the following approximation

$$(\lambda_m d / nl)^2, \quad (\lambda_m d / nl)^4 \ll \alpha_2 / \alpha_1, \quad (g)$$

then the characteristic equation of λ_m becomes:

$$\lambda_m^4 - 2BJ\lambda_m^2 + (1/3)J^2n^6 = 0 \quad (h)$$

These characteristic roots λ_m which satisfies the above equation and boundary conditions can be determined by an identical procedure for isotropic cylinder by L.H. Donnell (8).

Referring to Donnell's solution, we can obtain the following results:

(1) In short length cylinder,

for both ends supported ($J < 5.5$):

$$B = 1.18J^{1/4}, \quad n = 2.31J^{-1/4}$$

for both ends fixed ($J > 7.8$):

$$B = 1.29J^{1/4}, \quad n = 2.62J^{-1/4}$$

(i)

(2) In long cylinder region:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{for both ends supported: } J > 5.5 \\ \text{for both ends fixed: } J > 7.8 \end{array} \right\} \begin{array}{l} B = 0.77J^{1/2}, \\ n = 2 \end{array} \quad (j)$$

These formulas provide the buckling load.

Table I. Elastic Properties of Unidirectional Glass Filament Sheet

V_f	ρ	E_L	E_T	ν_L	G_{LT}	Remarks
0.3	1.87	2345	638	0.267	316	Filament: E-Glass, Matrix: Epoxy Resin
0.5	2.05	3675	975	0.251	503	
0.7	2.23	5005	1606	0.238	813	

(Note: Unit of E_L , E_T & G_{LT} in kg/mm^2)

Table II. Elastic Properties of Unidirectional Carbon Filament Sheet (6)

V_f	ρ	E_L	E_T	ν_L	G_{LT}	Remarks
0.3	1.714	13220	931	0.539	325	Filament: Type 1 Carbon Matrix: Epoxy Resin
0.5	1.790	21210	1031	0.536	430	
0.7	1.866	29180	1112	0.534	630	

(Note: Unit of E_L , E_T & G_{LT} in kg/mm^2)

Table III. Optimized Structural Index (SI_o) and Winding-Angle (θ_o) for GFWCylinder

V_f	ρ	$J < 5.5$			$J > 5.5$		
		SI_o	θ_o	E_1/E_2	SI_o	θ_o	E_1/E_2
0.3	1.87	21.99	68.90	0.358	25.09	61.4	0.457
0.5	2.05	25.61	68.16	0.358	29.63	61.2	0.457
0.7	2.23	29.23	68.73	0.412	33.94	60.8	0.519

(Note: Unit of θ_o in degree)

Table IV. Optimized Structural Index (SI_o) and Winding-Angle (θ_o) for CFWCylinder

V_f	ρ	$J < 5.5$			$J > 5.5$		
		SI_o	θ_o	E_1/E_2	SI_o	θ_o	E_1/E_2
0.3	1.714	43.42	71.3	0.101	53.93	66.6	0.133
0.5	1.790	50.57	71.6	0.0743	64.62	67.2	0.101
0.7	1.866	56.18	71.4	0.0643	73.37	66.6	0.0951

(Note: Unit of θ_o in degree)

Reference

- Hayashi Tsuyoshi : "On the elastic instability of orthogonal anisotropic cylindrical shells, especially the buckling loads due to compression, bending and torsion";
Journal of the Society of Naval Architects, Japan
No. 81 (1949), pp. 85-98.

Fig. 1 Geometry of Orthotropic Cylinder, Displacements and Torsional Shear Load.

Fig. 2 Stress-Resultants and Stress-Couples on a Cylinder Element

Fig. 3 Torsional Buckling Mode

$$\tan \varphi = \lambda_m d / (nl)$$

Fig. 4 Greenhill Buckling Mode for a Slender Tube

Fig. 5 Bias-Laminate Unit

Fig. 6 Unidirectional Basic Filament Sheet